

The reaction mixture, in a final volume of 1.0 ml, consisted of 0.05 M phosphate buffer (pH 8.2), 75 µg of trypsin (Sigma), 3.5×10^{-5} M BSA (substrate), glass distilled water and an appropriate amount of the compound to be tested. The compounds were dissolved in dimethyl formamide (DMF) and were tested at a final concentration of 5×10^{-4} M. The test compounds were preincubated with trypsin for 10 mins prior to the addition of BSA. After incubating for 5 mins the reaction was stopped by the addition of trichloroacetic acid (0.5 ml, 15% w/v). The acid soluble products of protein catabolism obtained after centrifugation were determined by the method of Lowry *et al*¹².

Pharmacological study: Anti-inflammatory activity of all the compounds was assessed against carrageenin induced oedema in rats following the method of Winter *et al*¹³.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds were tested for anti-proteolytic activity at 5×10^{-4} M concentration and the percent inhibitions are given in Table 1. An examination of anti-proteolytic activity in relation to the chemical structure revealed that various substituents at N' position of phenothiazine nucleus showed varying effects on activity. Substituted aminophenyl piperazine, aminophenyl morpholine, pyrrolidine showed better inhibition as compared to 4-amino morpholine, homopiperidine and substituted piperidine substituents at this position.

Maximum anti-proteolytic activity was observed in compound 13 in which there is 4-aminophenyl morpholine substituent at N' position of phenothiazine nucleus.

All the compounds were tested for their anti-inflammatory activity at a dose of 50 mg/kg administered orally (p. o.). Only five compounds (2, 5, 6, 12 and 13) inhibited the oedema formation. Their inhibitory activity ranged from 5.04-14.14% while other compounds had no effect.

The results of the present study show that the phenothiazines of the present series possess potent anti-proteolytic activity but poor anti-inflammatory activity. These findings, therefore, contradict the importance of proteolytic enzymes in acute phase of inflammation.

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Chemical Constituents of *Viburnum cotinifolium* (Fam : Caprifoliaceae)

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THE medicinal properties¹ of the plants of the genus *Viburnum* prompted us to chemically investigate *Viburnum cotinifolium*, on which there is no report of previous work. This has resulted in the isolation of two triterpenoids. One of these, C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺456), m.p. 285°, [α]_D+70° (CHCl₃) is a triterpenic acid which forms a methyl ester, C₃₁H₅₀O₃ (M⁺470), m.p. 168°, [α]_D+58° (CHCl₃), with diazomethane and a monoacetate, C₃₂H₅₀O₄ (M⁺498), m.p. 290°, [α]_D+70° (CHCl₃), with Ac₂O/py. It was identified as ursolic acid by direct comparison of the compound and its above derivatives with the respective authentic samples. The other compound, C₃₀H₅₀O₃ (M⁺442), m.p. 215°, [α]_D+65.3° (CHCl₃), is a triterpenediol which forms a diacetate, C₃₄H₅₄O₄ (M⁺526), m.p. 151° with Ac₂O/py. The physical constants and the spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and mass) data of the compound and its diacetyl derivative are indicative of an uvaol² structure for it. This was confirmed by establishing the identity of the compound with the LAH reduction product of the methyl ester of the congener triterpenic acid.

A further evidence confirming the ursane skeleton of the two triterpenoids was provided by a comparison of the ¹³C nmr spectral data of the diacetyl derivative of the triterpene-diol with those of erythrodiol diacetate prepared from an authentic sample of oleanolic acid. The carbon chemical shifts of the two compounds differ significantly in respect of their C-11, C-12, C-13, C-27 and the carbons concerning their ring E, while the remaining carbon atoms have almost identical δ_c values. Thus, the signals for C-11, C-13, C-19, C-21,

C-27, C-29 and C-30 of the former are shifted upfield by 6.3, 5.3, 6.5, 3.3, 2.7, 9.9 and 2.4 ppm respectively compared to those of the corresponding carbon atoms of the latter. On the other hand C-12, C-16, C-17, C-18, C-20 and C-22 of the former compound appear at lowerfields by 2.7, 1.0, 0.8, 11.8, 8.3 and 4.2 ppm respectively, than the corresponding carbon atoms of erythrodiol diacetate. Such differences of the δ_c values have already been shown^{8,4,5} to be diagnostic of isomeric pairs of ursane and oleanane derivatives and the above results provide further corroboration of the above generalisation.

Experimental

Air dried powdered aerial parts of *V. cotinifolium* (1 Kg) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and methanol. Concentration of the petrol extract deposited a white solid which was filtered. The solid and the filtrate were separately chromatographed over silica gel (60-100 mesh). Evaporation of the petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate from each chromatogram gave uvaol (total yield 0.04%), crystallised from methanol, m. p. 215°. ν_{\max}^{KBr} 3420 cm^{-1} (OH); ^1H nmr: δ_{ppm} 5.2, 1H, m ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{C}$); 3.36,

2H, AB_q ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{OH}$); 3.28, 1H, m ($-\text{CH}-\text{OH}$) and 0.8-1.1, 21H (7 C-methyls); MS: significant peaks at m/e (relative abundance) 442(4.1), 411(3.6), 235(4.2), 234(22.3), 217(2.5), 216(6.6), 208(3.0), 207(15.7), 205(3.1), 204(17.3), 203(100), 191(3.0), 190(3.7), 189(6.6), 187(3.4), 177(3.3), 176(3.5), 175(3.5), 161(3.1), 147(4.9), 145(4.6), 135(5.8), 134(4.1), 133(23.2) and 119(11.3). Diacetyl uvaol: ν_{\max} 1735 and 1245 cm^{-1} (OAc); ^1H nmr: δ_{ppm} 5.16, 1H, m ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{C}$); 3.83, 2H, AB_q ($-\text{CH}_2\text{OAc}$); 4.53, 1H, m ($-\text{CHOAc}$); 2.03, 6H, s ($-\text{O}-\text{C}-\text{Me}$);

0.86-1.23, 21H (7 C-methyls). ^{13}C nmr of uvaol diacetate: $^*\delta_{\text{ppm}}$ 38.3(C-1), 23.1(C-2), 80.4(C-3), 37.4(C-4), 55.0(C-5), 18.0(C-6), 32.5(C-7), 39.7(C-8), 47.4(C-9), 36.6(C-10), 17.1(C-11), 125.2(C-12), 138(C-13), 42(C-14), 26(C-15), 23.1(C-16), 36.5(C-17), 54.2(C-18), 39.6(C-19), 39.0(C-20), 30.6(C-21), 35.5(C-22), 27.8(C-23), 16.5(C-24), 15.5(C-25), 16.5(C-26), 23.1(C-27), 70.7(C-28), 23.1(C-29), 21.0(C-30),

170.3($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 20.8($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 170.1($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 21.0($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$). ^{13}C nmr of erythrodiol diacetate: $^*\delta_{\text{ppm}}$ 38.2(C-1), 23.4(C-2), 80.7(C-3), 37.6(C-4), 55.1(C-5), 18.1(C-6), 32.4(C-7), 39.6(C-8), 47.4(C-9), 36.7(C-10), 23.4(C-11), 122.5(C-12), 143.3(C-13), 41.5(C-14), 25.5(C-15), 22.1(C-16), 35.7(C-17),

42.4(C-18), 46.1(C-19), 30.7(C-20), 33.9(C-21), 31.3(C-22), 27.9(C-23), 16.6(C-24), 15.5(C-25), 16.6(C-26), 25.8(C-27), 70.5(C-28), 33.0(C-29), 23.4(C-30), 170.8($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 20.8($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 170.5($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 21.1($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$). [$^*\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$].

Further elution of the chromatograms with petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) afforded ursolic acid, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m. p. 285° (total yield 0.25%). The chloroform and the methanol extracts gave only traces of the above compounds.

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Chemical Examination of the Leaves and Stem Heartwood of *Tebebuia pentaphylla* (Linn) Hemsl (Bignoniaceae)

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TEBEBUIA pentaphylla (Linn) Hemsl [Syn. *Tecoma pentaphylla* Juss, *Pink tecomasalvador*, *Pink trumpet*, *Bignonia pentaphylla* (Linn)¹] is a medium sized tree, native to tropical America. It is planted in lawns and squares for flowers which appear on leafless shoots. The wood is light yellow to grey-brown, very hard and bears a superficial resemblance to oak. It is moderately light to fairly heavy, medium to coarse textured.